

TESTING OF ABOVE GROUND PERMANENT CONNECTIONS IN HIGH-VOLTAGE POWER FACILITY GROUNDING SYSTEMS

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Abstract:

Measuring of above ground permanent connections electrical resistance may be a difficult task to achieve, when the high-voltage power facility is in normal operating condition. In order to improve the susceptibility to the power frequency interference in the measurements, we present a measurement approach, which utilizes the DC test current of 100 A through the grounding grid connections to structures or equipment. The main advantage of the proposed approach is reflected in the fact that we create an algorithm for detection of above ground permanent connection with high value of electrical resistance. The criteria for evaluation of poor connection are empirically derived. Field test results justify and validate the proposed approach.

Key words: Above ground permanent connections, Testing, Interference, DC test current

ISPITIVANJE PERMANENTNIH NADZEMNIH SPOJEVA U SISTEMU UZEMLJENJA VISOKONAPONSKOG POSTROJENJA

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Abstract:

Merenje električne otpornosti permanentnih nadzemnih spojeva u sistemu uzemljenja predstavlja složen istraživački zadatak u okolnostima kada je visokonaponsko postrojenje u normalnom radnom režimu. Kako bi se iz rezultata merenja eliminisala interferencija (dominantno 50 Hz), koja je prisutna u uzemljivačkim sistemima aktivnih visokonaponskih postrojenja, u radu je predstavljen metod koji se bazira na propuštanju jednosmerne ispitne struje (100 A) kroz spojeve zemljovoda sa nosačima visokonaponske opreme ili čelične strukture. U cilju automatizacije obrade sirovih mernih podataka, kreiran je algoritam procedure ispitivanja. Kriterijumi na osnovu kojih se donosi ocena o potencijalno lošem spoju su empirijski ustanovljeni. Rezultati predstavljeni u radu potvrđuju praktičnu implementaciju navedenog pristupa.

Ključne reči: Permanentni nadzemni spoj, Ispitivanja, Interferencija, DC ispitna struja

1. INTRODUCTION

The above ground permanent connections of ground risers to structures or frameworks of equipment are the integral part of the high-voltage substation grounding systems. These, so called heavy-duty connectors [1] can carry ground fault currents, which values can exceed tens of kA. Experience has shown that the ground fault current can cause a lot of damage to equipment and pose a safety hazard to personnel when it does not find a low-impedance path to the ground grid.

Therefore, it makes sense to periodically check and verify the quality of the ground grid connections to structures and equipment, otherwise the connections used to join the ground risers to equipment and structures (hereinafter referred to as above ground permanent connections [2]). The jointing methods used in grounding system include mechanical (bolted connection or hydraulic), brazed, exothermic and welded. In this work our focus is on above ground bolted permanent connections (AGBPC), more precisely, one or two – bolt parallel groove connections.

AGBPC must be mechanically robust, have good corrosion resistance and low electrical resistance. It is generally accepted fact, that a good mechanical joint is also a good electric joint [1]. In many cases, this may not be true because different factors such as: the correct selection of connecting bolts, tightening of bolts and nuts to the correct torque and surface preparation can distort the value of the predicted electrical resistance. According to our experience, because the electrical resistance value of AGBPC is expected to be very low, periodical field tests are essential and need to be performed in order to verify the fulfillment of the expected demands. So far, as far as the authors know, either one research paper did not pay attention of above ground permanent connection field testing.

Measuring of power connections electrical resistance was not the subject of actual standards which are dealing with techniques for measuring of the electrical characteristics of grounding systems [3 - 5]. Field tests are also not a part of a standard [2] which extensively deals with permanent connections used in substation grounding. Many researchers have tried to find a reliable method for grounding grid integrity testing [6 - 9] and detection of poor underground connections. In accordance with the aforementioned in [9] states: *“The objective of ground grid integrity measurement is to determine whether the equipment, structures, or enclosure grounds are connected to the grounding electrode or ground grid with low resistance. The resistance value of such connections is expected to be very low (100 $\mu\Omega$ or less)”*. On the other hand, in [10 - 11] a bonding resistance of 1 m Ω or less is considered as a high quality bond. Those allegations have served as a good foundation for our further research work.

In this paper, we will document our measurement campaign that is based on the DC voltage testing of AGBPC by measuring its electrical resistance. The measurements were successfully conducted in a substation 400/220/110 kV (Pančevo 2, Serbia). During the measurement the substation was in normal operating condition.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the environment and setup, as well as the methodology that we follow throughout our experiments. In Section 3, detailed discussion of the test results is presented. Section 4 briefly summarizes the results and draws relevant conclusions.

2. MEASUREMENT METHOD

From the authors' experience a convenient test method for AGBPC electrical resistance measurement should be performed when the high-voltage substation is in normal operating conditions. However, in this case the test signal may be affected by power system frequency interference and its harmonics. Therefore, in order to improve the signal-to-interference ratio, a substantially high AC current should be injected into the permanent connection under test, which still does not guarantee an acceptable measurement uncertainty. In order to eliminate power frequency interference, we present an approach which uses the DC test current of 100 A. Using DC, the effect of AC stray currents, which are normally exists in grounding system of high-voltage power facility in normal operating condition, is eliminated by measuring system because it measures the DC test current and it generates DC voltage drops. The measurement uncertainty is reduced to the measurement system error that can be precisely calculated. Selection of relatively low test current is based on many of our experiments previously conducted at different substations. In this context, we have experimented with AGBPC which were made of different materials. More precisely, we have experimented with two types of AGBPC which are commonly used in high-

Fig. 2 Measurement processing flowchart

3. FIELD TESTING

According to the above described procedure, the AGBPC electrical resistance measurements have been conducted at eleven locations covering both types of AGBPC that are commonly used in high-voltage power facilities in Serbia. Due to space limitation, here we provide only the measurement results for a substation rated voltage 400/220/110 kV (Pančevo 2, Serbia). The selection of the named power facility was influenced by the fact that, despite the large number of unreconstructed AGPBC made of brass (Fig 3 (a)), when the adaptation of certain high-voltage equipment was performed, besides mounting new high-voltage equipment and reconstruction of the grounding system, a new permanent connection that are made using an alloy of newer technologies are also installed (Figure 3 (b)). In this way, in addition to mutual comparison of test results on old (unreconstructed) AGPBC, a comparative analysis of the test results of unreconstructed and reconstructed AGPBC can be performed.

Fig. 3 AGBPC made of brass (a), AGBPC made of low-chromium white iron (b)

In order to localize AGBPC with high value of electrical resistance, we performed analysis and evaluation of the test results according to algorithm procedure.

Fig. 4a shows the layout plan of the characteristic locations (HV equipment in power facility rated voltage 110 kV) in the substation under test. The measurement results, i.e., the electrical resistance for each AGBPC are also shown in Fig. 4a.

Fig. 4a Layout plan of the AGBPC under test. Abbreviations: BD-busbar disconnector; CB-circuit breaker; CC-control cubicle; CT-current transformer; LD-line disconnector; SA-surge arrester; VT-voltage transformer.

According to algorithm procedure, we have found the AGBPC that need intervention (see Fig. 4b) based on the following facts:

- The electrical resistance at location no. 36 is 1.863 mΩ. For AGBPC made of brass the maximum value of electrical resistance should not exceed 1 mΩ. $1.863 \text{ m}\Omega > 1 \text{ m}\Omega$ (fail).
- The electrical resistance at location no. 37 is 1.863 mΩ. For AGBPC made of brass the maximum value of electrical resistance should not exceed 1 mΩ. $23 \text{ m}\Omega > 1 \text{ m}\Omega$ (fail).
- The electrical resistance at location no. 38 is 16.574 mΩ. For AGBPC made of brass the maximum value of electrical resistance should not exceed 1 mΩ. $16.574 \text{ m}\Omega > 1 \text{ m}\Omega$ (fail).
- The electrical resistance at location no. 39 is 2.720 mΩ. For AGBPC made of brass the maximum value of electrical resistance should not exceed 1 mΩ. $2.720 \text{ m}\Omega > 1 \text{ m}\Omega$ (fail).
- The electrical resistance at location no. 40 is 1.599 mΩ. For AGBPC made of brass the maximum value of electrical resistance should not exceed 1 mΩ. $1.599 \text{ m}\Omega > 1 \text{ m}\Omega$ (fail).

- (f) The electrical resistance at location no. 43 is 7.218 mΩ. For AGBPC made of brass the maximum value of electrical resistance should not exceed 1 mΩ. $7.218 \text{ m}\Omega > 1 \text{ m}\Omega$ (fail).
- (g) The electrical resistance at location no. 47 is 1.3 mΩ. For AGBPC made of brass the maximum value of electrical resistance should not exceed 1 mΩ. $1.3 \text{ m}\Omega > 1 \text{ m}\Omega$ (fail).
- (h) The electrical resistance at location no. 49 is 5.273 mΩ. For AGBPC made of brass the maximum value of electrical resistance should not exceed 1 mΩ. $5.273 \text{ m}\Omega > 1 \text{ m}\Omega$ (fail).
- (i) The electrical resistance at location no. 67 is 0.152 mΩ. For AGBPC made of low-chromium white iron electrical resistance should not exceed 0.1 mΩ. $0.152 \text{ m}\Omega > 0.1 \text{ m}\Omega$ (fail).

Fig. 4b Final assessment of AGBPC with poor electrical resistance

After intervention, which was reflected in the disassembly and cleaning of joints and their re-assembly respecting the tightening torque bolts recommended by the manufacturer, we have been repeating the tests, and all the values now satisfy the empirically derived criteria (see Fig 4.c).

The comparative analysis of the measurement results at the locations labeled with fail (Fig. 4b) and locations after intervention (Fig. 4c) is shown in Table 1. The calculation of the expanded uncertainty interval ($\pm U$) was carried out according to [12].

Fig. 4c Test results after intervention

Table 1 Analysis of the suspected locations before and after the intervention

Location	R_{nsc} [mΩ]	$\pm U_{nsc}$ [mΩ]	$R_{nsc} \pm U_{nsc}$ [mΩ]	R_{ai} [mΩ]	$\pm U_{ai}$ [mΩ]	$R_{ai} \pm U_{ai}$ [mΩ]	Improvement of AGBPC electrical resistance
36	1.863	0.038	1.863±0.038	0.110	0.002	0.110±0.002	16.94 times
37	23	0.483	23±0.483	0.292	0.006	0.292±0.006	78.77 times
38	16.574	0.330	16.574±0.330	0.120	0.002	0.120±0.002	138.12 times
39	2.720	0.057	2.720±0.057	0.130	0.003	0.130±0.003	20.92 times
40	1.599	0.032	1.599±0.032	0.111	0.002	0.111±0.002	14.40 times
43	7.218	0.147	7.218±0.147	0.308	0.006	0.308±0.006	23.44 times
47	1.300	0.027	1.300±0.027	0.210	0.005	0.210±0.005	6.19 times
49	5.273	0.112	5.273±0.112	0.115	0.002	0.115±0.002	45.85 times
67	0.152	0.003	0.152±0.003	0.022	0.0005	0.022±0.0005	6.90 times

Legend:

R_{nsc} – AGBPC electrical resistance measurement results that not satisfy the criteria; U_{nsc} – expanded uncertainty interval of R_{nsc} ;
 R_{ai} – AGBPC electrical resistance measurement results after intervention; U_{ai} – expanded uncertainty interval of R_{ai} .

Test results presented in Table 1, justify and validate the proposed approach. One can see, that the value of unreconstructed AGBPC electrical resistance made of brass has improved from 6.19 to 138.12 times after intervention, and on AGBPC made of low-chromium white iron 6.9 times.

Generally, a contact based on a low-chromium white iron is much better than the contact based on the brass. Therefore, contact based on a low-chromium white iron is less sensitive to the mechanical imperfections (insufficiently tightening screws).

4. CONCLUSION

The AGBPC are an essential part of the power facilities grounding system. Their reliability is often ignored, because of their robustness. Therefore, electrical resistance measurement is the only way that determines the condition of the AGBPC. The objective of this paper was to describe an improvement of the measurement methodology. Furthermore, we have presented and documented an improved high-current measurement method which uses the DC test current of 100 A, with a procedure that should be taken to assess the AGBPC with poor electrical resistance. The procedures presented in this paper can be used as a guide when carrying out test analysis of a large-sized high-voltage power facility.

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6. REFERENCES

- [1] P. G. Slade, *Electrical Contacts Principles and Applications*, second ed., CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group, 2014.
- [2] IEEE Standard for Qualifying Permanent Connections Used in Substation Grounding, *IEEE Standard 837-2002*.
- [3] IEEE Guide for Safety in AC Substation Grounding, *IEEE Standard 80-2000*.
- [4] IEEE Guide for Measuring Earth Resistivity, Ground Impedance, and Earth Surface Potentials of a Ground System, *IEEE Standard 81-2012*.
- [5] EN 50522, *Earthing of power installations exceeding 1 kV a.c.*, Nov. 2010.
- [6] J. He, R. Zeng, and B. Zhang, *Methodology and Technology for Power System Grounding*, John Wiley & Sons, Singapore Pte. Ltd., 2013., Ch. 11.
- [7] B. Zhang, Z. Zhao, X. Cui, L. Li, Diagnosis of breaks in substation's grounding grid by using the electromagnetic method, *IEEE Trans. Magnetics* vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 473-476, 2002.
- [8] Y. Chikarov, A New Approach to Monitor the Integrity of Grounding Grids, PhD Thesis, Auckland University of Technology, Auckland, New Zeland, 2013.
- [9] P. Gill, Electrical power system grounding and ground resistance measurements, in: *Electrical Power Equipment Maintenance and Testing*, second ed., CRC Press, 2008.
- [10] Grounding and Bonding for Network Facilities – Design Fundamentals, ATT-TP-76416-001, Issue 1, Jan. 2004.
- [11] Grounding and Bonding in Command, Control, Communications, Computer, Intelligence, Surveillance and Reconnaissance Facilities, Technical Manual TM 5-690, Headquarters Department of the Army, Feb. 2002.
- [12] Evaluation of Measurement Data – Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement, International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland, Sep. 2008.